

Research

Grid-Connected Three Phase Hybrid AC to DC Microgrid Controlling System using Bidirectional Converter

Khan Shahnewaz Sohagh^{1}, Xiaoqing Han¹, Lei Wang¹*

¹School of Electrical Engineering, Taiyuan University of Technology, Shanxi, China

**Corresponding author*

Accepted: 13 November, 2019; Online: 21 November, 2019

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3549833>

Abstract: *Micro grids are emerging as one of the promising solutions to integrate various types of distributed renewable energy sources with the utility grid. Though the existing grids are AC grids, today's electrical loads comprising of power electronic based equipment and distributed renewable energy generation make DC micro grids more attractive. However, an individual AC micro grid and DC micro grid requires multiple conversions of power at the user end for DC loads and AC loads respectively, resulting in less efficient system. Thus, hybrid AC/DC micro grid seems to be the best solution to avoid substantial energy losses in multiple conversions. However, there are several technical challenges in the implementation of hybrid AC/DC micro grid, which need to be addressed. This paper presents an overview of hybrid AC/DC micro grid and discusses the important key issues and challenges to be overcome for its practical implementation.*

Keywords: *Micro grids, AC, DC*

Background

Recently, renewable energy sources such as wind, solar and small hydro based power plants have gained considerable attention worldwide due to global warming, fast depletion of fossil fuels along with growing energy demand. Generally, power generation from these renewable energy sources is in the range of tens of kilowatts to fraction of megawatts and due to this, these energy sources are usually connected at distribution level in order to reduce power losses in long transmission [1]. Therefore, these sources are also called as Distributed Generations (DGs).

The application of DGs is expected to provide benefits in terms of reliability and security of power, economics of power generation, carbon dioxide emission and power quality etc. At the same time, they may introduce new challenges into the system operation and control. The concept of “micro grid” has been evolved for smooth integration and control of DGs with the utility grid. A micro grid comprises of low voltage distributed systems with distributed generations, storage devices, loads and interconnecting switches. A micro grid can be operated in three modes of operation viz. island mode, grid-connected mode and transition between the first two modes. The operation of micro grids provide advantages of higher flexibility, better power quality, controllability, efficiency of operation, and bidirectional power flow between the utility grid and the micro grid in the grid connected mode of operation [2]. AC micro grids (ACMG) have been proposed [3-4] to utilize the existing AC grid technologies, protection and standards. However, power generation from various DGs such as photovoltaic arrays and fuel cells is DC power, which is to be converted into AC power through power electronic interface. DC/AC inverter for connecting them with the AC utility grid. This AC power is again converted back into DC power required by today’s electrical loads such as Uninterrupted Power Supply (UPS), fluorescent lights, variable motor drives and hybrid electric vehicles. Thus, an individual AC micro grid is less efficient due to more power losses are occurring in multiple conversions. Besides this, synchronization, stability, and reactive power requirement are its inherent demerits [5]. DC micro grids (DCMG) [6-8], are emerging as a better alternative due to the above mentioned reasons for renewable energy based DGs. However, power generation from the sources such as diesel generator, small hydro turbine with synchronous generator and photovoltaic panels etc. as well as the electrical loads are a mix of AC and DC power. Thus, an individual DCMG cannot completely eliminate the losses occurring in multiple stage conversions, though the losses occurring in DC/DC conversions are lesser than those occurring in AC/DC or DC/AC conversions. In an individual ACMG, AC loads require single stage conversion and DC loads require multiple conversions. Similarly, in an individual DCMG, DC loads require single stage conversions and AC loads require multiple stage conversions. Thus, a hybrid AC/DC micro grid (HADMG) is more beneficial; to facilitate the connection of various renewable AC and DC power sources and loads with the power system

in order to minimize the conversion losses. Since the operational issues of HADMG are more complicated than those of an individual ACMG and DCMG, these need to be investigated.

System Description

In Figure 1, shows the hybrid AC to DC bidirectional micro grid system. Which is consist of AC side DC side and for power flow synchronization there use bidirectional AC to DC converter. The aim of this converter is to convert the power DC to AC also AC to DC.

FIGURE 1: an AC to DC hybrid micro grid controlling System.

The system, as shown in figure 2, consists of Three phase AC-DC converter, AC side is connected to grid, DC side connected to loads and source is considered. Appropriate sensors are used for implementing the closed loop control. The converter's dynamic response is verified with different combinations of system dynamics such as variation in load, variation in source, and variation in both load and source. The total system is consisting of DC-DC Boost converter part which is connected PV array. This converter is controlled by close loop control system. This output is connected with SIX IGBT diode of inverter, then this wave is connected to LCL compensator. This LCL filter works to compensate the harmonics of current. The power of AC part is connected with DC power through Bidirectional converter.

FIGURE 2. System block diagram.

generator is connected to three phase bridge rectifiers to convert AC into DC power source. The control of the DC power is done by varying PLL manually. DC source can also be implemented with simple controlled rectifier connected to grid through isolation transformer. Note that the AC source considered here is the grid only. The parameters for the system described are shown in Table 1. This paper focuses on AC-DC converter control strategy for different modes of operation - rectification, inversion, and reactive power support, as explained in the next section.

Parameters	Value
AC Bus Voltage(V)	311v
AC microgrid active power reference values(P_{ac}^*)	13 kw
DC Bus Voltage(V)	750v
DC microgrid active power reference values(P_{dc}^*)	20kw
DC filter capacitor(C_{dc})	1400uF
filter inductor(L_a, L_b, L_c)	5mH
filter capacitor(C_a, C_b, C_c)	47uF

The different modes of converter operations and brief understanding about each mode are described in subsequent subsections. It is to be noted that the voltage and current waveforms are in phase for the rectification mode, so the product of the voltage and current is positive which means the converter is consuming the power (power is transferring from AC side to DC side). If the voltage and current waveforms are 180° out of phase, then converter is said to be operating in

$$I_a(t) = \sqrt{2} I \sin(\omega t - \phi),$$

$$V_a(t) = \sqrt{2} V \sin \omega t,$$

$$I_b(t) = \sqrt{2} I \sin(\omega t + 120 - \phi),$$

$$V_b = \sqrt{2} V \sin(\omega t + 120),$$

$$I_c(t) = \sqrt{2} I \sin(\omega t - 120 - \phi),$$

$$V_c = \sqrt{2} \sin(\omega t - 120),$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} i_d \\ i_q \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\theta_1) & \cos\left(\theta_1 - \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) & \cos\left(\theta_1 + \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) \\ \sin(\theta_1) & \sin\left(\theta_1 - \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) & \sin\left(\theta_1 + \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) \end{pmatrix} * \begin{pmatrix} i_a \\ i_b \\ i_c \end{pmatrix}$$

4.2. Shut-Down Mode

In this mode, the converter is neither delivering nor absorbing the power, all the gate control pulses to the converter (Q1-Q6) are set to zero. This mode appears in two situations, one is when the available DC power source is exactly equal to DC load demand and the other is for protecting the converter during abnormal conditions.

$$\begin{bmatrix} I_{a_{ref}} \\ I_{b_{ref}} \\ I_{c_{ref}} \end{bmatrix} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & 1 & 0 \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & -\frac{1}{2} & -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \end{bmatrix} * \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos(\omega t) & -\sin(\omega t) \\ 0 & \sin(\omega t) & \cos(\omega t) \end{bmatrix} * \begin{bmatrix} I_0 \\ I_d \\ I_q \end{bmatrix}$$

It is well known that the DC bus voltage deviate from its nominal value due to DC load and DC power source mismatch. Whenever the DC bus voltage deviates from the reference value, there is an error voltage either positive or negative depending upon the available DC power is higher or less than the DC load. In the same way the zero-error voltage indicates that the DC source power available is exactly meeting the DC load demand. Using this command signal, the shut-down mode can be set by comparing the error voltage with zero.

4.3. Unity Power Factor Mode

In this mode, a converter operates to draw unity power factor (UPF) current irrespective of its operation as rectifier or inverter. This mode can be subdivided as UPF rectification and UPF inversion mode. Whenever the DC load is more than the DC source, the DC bus is required to draw power from AC source, rectifier operation. In this case controller checks for the reactive power reference, if the reactive power reference is zero, it indicates that the system needs to be operated in UPF mode, as the case is rectification operation, it is termed as UPF rectification mode. If the DC source is more than the DC load, the converter needs to transfer power to AC source., inversion operation. As discussed above, if the reactive power reference is zero, this case

is termed as UPF inversion mode. Rectification and inversion operation are detected by using the DC bus voltage error 'e'. If the DC source is less than the DC load, the bus voltage decreases below reference voltage, If the DC source is more than the DC load, the DC bus voltage increase above the reference voltage, In this way, controller automatically adapts its mode of operation based on the circuit conditions. In both the modes the controller is designed in such a way that to draw or inject pure sinusoidal waveform, THD should be very low.

4.4. Reactive Power Compensation Mode

This mode is used to supply or absorb reactive power from the grid when the grid voltage is not within the limits. The control loop can be added to output the reference reactive power command by inputting the AC voltage, which becomes closed loop control of reactive power compensation. Other possibility adopted here is to set the reactive power reference manually and by using the conversion block corresponding phase angle can be generated. The generated phase angle will be added to the phase of AC current reference (which is obtained from PLL); the resultant phase is passed through unit sine block to generated sinusoidal reference current. In this way the reactive power compensation can be included in the control strategy. Now it is required to make the controller to adapt suitable switching scheme as discussed above, the switching table is shown in table 2. The reactive power compensation mode can be identified by comparing the Q_{ref} with zero, if the Q_{ref} is not zero then the controller changes to the reactive power compensation mode and accordingly it chooses the corresponding switching scheme as devised in table 2.

Angle	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6
$0 \leq \theta < \frac{\pi}{2}$	1	1	0	1	0	0
$\frac{\pi}{3} \leq \theta < \frac{2\pi}{3}$	1	0	0	1	1	0
$\frac{2\pi}{3} \leq \theta < \pi$	1	0	1	0	1	0
$\pi \leq \theta < 4\pi/3$	0	0	1	0	1	1
$4\pi/3 \leq \theta < 5\pi/3$	0	1	1	0	0	1
$5\pi/3 \leq \theta < 2\pi$	0	1	0	1	0	1

Isolated Mode

When the hybrid grid operates in the islanding mode, the boost converter and the back to back ac/dc/ac converter may operate in the on MPPT or off MPPT based on system power balance and energy constraints. The main converter acts as a voltage source or converter mode for the smooth power exchange between ac and dc links. The dc-link voltage is maintained by either the battery or the boost converter based on system operating condition. Powers under various load and Supply conditions should be balanced.

Simulation Results and Discussion

The AC-DC microgrid system for home electricity is simulated for the 750V DC bus voltages. The parameters used for the system is listed in Table 1. The system is tested with resistive load for different modes of operation, rectification mode, inversion mode, and simultaneous switching of the mode, based on the power availability. For showing the controller's response to be able to meet the load demand, different case scenarios of load and power generation are considered here and listed in the table 3.

Case no.	Case description	Remarks
1	Performance in UPF, Rectification mode	$Q_{ref} = 0$
2	Performance in UPF inversion mode	$Q_{ref} = 0$
3	Switching of modes in UPF mode	$Q_{ref} = 0$, and DC load equal and more than the DC available source at 0.72 sec and 0.76 sec, respectively
4	Inversion and rectification in reactive power compensation mode	DC load equal and more than the DC available source at 0.72 sec and 0.76 sec, respectively
5	Performance of converter to be able to switch dynamically with all modes	DC load equal and more than the DC available source at 0.72 sec and 0.76 sec, respectively

Case-1: Performance in Rectification Mode (UPF)

In any case, a controller checks Q_{ref} and then the error voltage. As the reactive power references zero, converter switches to UPF mode. Since, there is no power source available on DC side apart from the 20 KW load, the controller has to give control pulses to operate converter in rectification mode. As the DC bus voltage is below the reference level, mode changing signal will set the controller to give rectification pulses, which are predefined in look up table. This case is simulated by connecting the 20 KW load on DC side with no DC source. From the obtained results, as shown in figure 3, it is clearly seen that the controller made the converter to operate in

rectification mode by choosing corresponding switching pulses and supplied 20 KW power to the DC load from the grid.

FIGURE 3. Simulation results for Case 1.

Case 2: Performance in Inversion Mode (UPF)

In this case also Q_{ref} is set to zero, converter switches to either UPF or shut down mode based on the value of 'e'. Due to favorable weather, energy is available on the DC side, since there is no load connected, the DC bus voltage starts raising and makes the error voltage negative (means DC voltage becoming more than the reference value) with that, controller generates the switching pulses to operate the converter in UPF-inversion mode as shown in figure 4, so that the generated power on DC side will be transferred to the AC side and the maximum output current impact is about 50A.

$$THD_0 = \sqrt{\frac{V^2_0 - V^2_{01}}{V^2_{01}}}$$

FIGURE 4. Waveforms for output current.

It can be observed in the Figure 4 that the AC current waveform is out phase to the voltage, which means grid consuming the power. For the clear representation, power waveforms also

drawn, P (active power) is negative and Q (reactive power) is zero. In addition, the DC bus voltage is maintained within the limits and current injected to the grid is observed pure sinusoidal with UPF and measured THD is $\approx 1.25\%$. This case is to realize the practical scenarios like the supply situation during holidays (where people use to go out and no load connected in the home) or due to favorable weather conditions.

Case-3: Switching of Modes in Unity Power Factor Operation

In this case initially some load connected and DC side source can be assumed as solar PV. The DC load is started increasing in a way that DC source at 0.72 sec it is able to supply all the DC load demand. As the error voltage is zero at 0.72 sec, the converter switches to shut down mode and stops the control pulses. As shown in Figure 4, the current at 0.72 sec is zero and the instantaneous power 'p' is zero, please note that the zero power reflected on the instantaneous power but the active and reactive power shown are zero after a cycle, this is because for calculating P and Q measurement blocks waits for a cycle to calculate the average value of any periodic waveforms. With this note instantaneous power will not be shown in subsequent figures. But at 0.76 sec, there is an increment in DC load which leads the DC bus voltage to drop from the reference value. So, the error 'e' became positive and the controller switched to UPF rectification mode as the Q_{ref} is zero. The controller releases the switching pulses to the converter to operate in UPF rectification mode, which is cleared from the voltage, current, and power waveforms shown in Figure 5. This case is to realize the converter performance, where a system having solar PV, the DC load during the afternoon to evening increases and DC source decreases gradually.

FIGURE 5. Waveforms for case 3.

Experimental Results and Discussion

The performance of bidirectional converter with improved control strategy is verified on lab scale experimental set-up with the control circuit implemented in the real-time digital simulation platform [12]. As shown in, a system considered for hardware consists of three-phase AC-DC

converter, AC side is connected to grid through 230 V transformer, DC side connected to loads (resistive for the sake of simplicity) and source. All the system parameters, as indicated in Table 1, are taken in lab scaled range for ensuring safety. The control pulses generation and signal monitoring are done using the real time digital simulator. The Simulink diagram, is developed in such a way that to be compatible for the RT-Lab, OPAL RT software platform. The whole simulation has to be divided into two subsystems namely SM Subsystem and SC Subsystem. The work is still on process.

Figure 7. Lab-scale experimental setup.

Conclusion

The improved control strategy for three phase bidirectional AC-DC converter is presented, with different cases of load scenarios and generation change on DC side, for the power flow management in hybrid AC/DC microgrid. The simulation is performed to validate the performance improvement. Also, the experimental analysis has been carried out on lab-scale hardware set-up with the control circuit implemented in the real-time digital simulation platform for dynamic performance verification. The simulation and experimental results showed that the converter with improved control strategy optimally manages the bidirectional (active and reactive) power flow with additional PI controller for reactive power. It is also observed that the converter is capable to supply or absorb the reactive power (both leading and lagging power factor) to the grid. The converter is able to operate in reduced switching loss scheme in both rectification and inversion mode (while power factor is unity), however the switching loss is more in the case of reactive power compensation mode. It is also noticed that the THD of current waveform is well below of 5% in all the cases performed which is IEEE standard.

Reference

□ R. A. Kaushik, and N. M. Pindoriya, “A hybrid AC-DC microgrid: Opportunities & key issues in implementation,” 2014 IEEE international conference on Green Computing, Communication and Electrical Engineering (ICGCCEE'14). Coimbatore, India, March 6-8, 2014.

[\[Google Scholar\]](#)

- X. Liu, P. Wang, and P. C. Loh, “A hybrid AC/DC microgrid and its coordination control,” *IEEE Trans. Smart Grid*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp.278–286. doi:10.1109/TSG.2011.2116162., June 2011.
[\[Crossref\]](#), [\[Web of Science ®\]](#)
[, \[Google Scholar\]](#)
- P. C. Loh, D. Li, Y. K. Chai, and F. Blaabjerg, “Autonomous control of interlinking converter with energy storage in hybrid AC–DC microgrid,” *IEEE Trans. Ind. Appl.*, vol. 49, no. 3, pp. 1374–1382. doi:10.1109/TIA.2013.2252319, May–June 2013.
[\[Crossref\]](#), [\[Web of Science ®\]](#)
[, \[Google Scholar\]](#)
- P. C. Loh, D. Li, Y. K. Chai, and F. Blaabjerg, “Autonomous operation of hybrid microgrid with AC and DC subgrids,” *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 28, no. 5, pp.2214–2223, doi:10.1109/TPEL.2012.2214792., May 2013.
[\[Crossref\]](#), [\[Web of Science ®\]](#)
[, \[Google Scholar\]](#)
- R. A. Kaushik, and N. M. Pindoriya, “Power flow control of hybrid AC-DC microgrid using master-slave technique, 2014 IEEE Conference on Energy Conversion (CENCON), Malaysia, Oct 2014.
[\[Google Scholar\]](#)
- L. Wang, S. Chai, D. Yoo, L. Gan, and K. Ng, *PID and Predictive Control of Electrical Drives and Power Converters using MATLAB/Simulink*. Hoboken, NJ: Wiley-IEEE Press, 2014.
[\[Google Scholar\]](#)
- Y. H. Liao, “A novel reduced switching loss bidirectional ac/dc converter PWM strategy with feed forward control for grid-tied microgrid systems,” *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 29, no. 3, pp. 1500–1513. doi:10.1109/TPEL.2013.2260872., March 2014
[\[Crossref\]](#), [\[Web of Science ®\]](#)
[, \[Google Scholar\]](#)
- J. H. Chow, F. F. Wu, and J. A. Momoh, *Applied mathematics for restructured electric power systems: optimization, control, and computational intelligence*. New York, NY: Springer, 2005.
[\[Google Scholar\]](#)
- P. C. Loh, D. Li, Y. K. Chai, and F. Blaabjerg, “Autonomous operation of hybrid microgrid with ac and dc subgrids,” *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 28, no. 5, pp. 2214–2223, doi:10.1109/TPEL.2012.2214792., May 2013.
[\[Crossref\]](#), [\[Web of Science ®\]](#)
[, \[Google Scholar\]](#)
- R. Majumder, G. Ledwich, A. Ghosh, S. Chakrabarti and F. Zare, "Droop Control of Converter-Interfaced Microsources in Rural Distributed Generation," in *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, vol. 25, no. 4, pp
[\[Crossref\]](#), [\[Web of Science ®\]](#)

, [\[Google Scholar\]](#)

□ Festo didactic – labvolt series, Wind turbine emulator https://www.labvolt.com/solutions/50-8968-30_turbine_emulator

[\[Google Scholar\]](#)

□ Opal-RT, Hardware-in-the-Loop Simulation. [Online]. Available at: <http://www.opal-rt.com/about-hardware-loop-simulation>. Accessed: 2016.

[\[Google Scholar\]](#)

About the Authors:

Mr. KHAN SHAHNEWAZ SOHAGH was born in khulna, Bangladesh in 1993. He received the B.Sc degree in electrical and electronics engineering from Independent University of Bangladesh (IUB), Dhaka, Bangladesh, in 2015. Now he doing his M.Sc degree from Taiyuan University of Technology (TYUT), Shanxi, China. His current research interests include power electronic converters, active and hybrid filters, the application of power electronics in renewable energy systems, and power quality compensation systems.

XIAOQING HAN received the B., M., and Ph.D. degrees from the College of Electrical and Power Engineering, Taiyuan University of Technology, Taiyuan, China, in 1985, 1990 and 2009 respectively. She is currently a Professor with Taiyuan University of Technology, Taiyuan, China. Her research interests include power system simulation, stability analysis, and integration of renewable sources. Prof. Han was the recipient of the Science and Technology Award of Shanxi Province in 2002, 2006, 2008 and 2016.

LEI WANG was born in Shanxi, China, in 1985. He received the M. degrees in electrical engineering from Taiyuan University of Technology, Taiyuan, China, in 2010. His current research interests include power electronic converters, active and hybrid filters, the application of power electronics in renewable energy systems, and power quality compensation systems.

© 2019 by the authors. TWASP, NY, USA. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

